

II-NORMAL SPACES IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Hamant kumar

Department of Mathematics,

Government Degree College, Bilaspur-Rampur, 244921, U.P. (India)

Abstract. The aim of this paper is to introduce and study a new class of spaces, called ii-normal spaces. The relationships among β^*g -normal, s-normal, α -normal, γ -normal and ii-normal spaces are investigated. Moreover, we introduce the forms of generalized ii-closed (briefly gii-closed) and ii-generalized closed (briefly iig-closed) functions. We obtain characterizations of ii-normal spaces, properties of the forms of generalized ii-closed functions and preservation theorems.

Key Words: ii-open, gii-closed and iig-closed sets; ii-normal, s-normal, α -normal and β^*g -normal spaces; ii-closed and ii-gii-closed functions.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 54A05, 54C08, 54C10, 54D15.

1. Introduction

Normality is an important topological property and hence it is of significance both from intrinsic interest as well as from applications view point to obtain factorizations of normality in terms of weaker topological properties. In 1937, Stone [21] introduced the concept of regular-open sets. In 1963, Levine [13] introduced the notion of semi-open sets and obtained their properties. In 1965, Njastad [19] introduced the notion of α -open sets and obtained their properties. In 1970, Levine [14] initiated the investigation of g-closed sets in topological spaces, since then many modifications of g-closed sets were defined and investigated by a large number of topologists. In 1978, Maheshwari [15] introduced the notion of s-normal spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 1983, Abd El-Monsef [1] introduced the notion of β -open sets. In 1987, Bhattacharyya and Lahiri [6] introduced the concepts of sg-closed sets. In 1990, Arya and Nour [3] introduced the concepts of g-closed sets. In 1994, Maki et al [16] introduced the concepts of $g\alpha$ -closed and αg -closed sets. In 2007, Ekicii [8] introduced the notion of γ -normal spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2008, Maki et al. [17] introduced the concepts s^*g -closed sets and s^* -normal spaces, and obtained their characterizations. In 2009, Benchalli [5] introduced the notion of α -normal spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2015, Sharma and Hamant [20] introduced the concepts of β^*g -closed sets and β^* -normal spaces, and obtained their characterizations. In 2019, Hamant [11] introduced the concept of β^*g -normal spaces, and obtained their characterizations. In 2019, Mohammed and Abdullah [2] introduced the concepts of ii-open sets and obtained their properties. In 2019, Hamant [10] introduced the concepts of ii-separation axioms and ii-closed functions.

2. Preliminaries

In what follows, spaces always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated and $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ (or simply $f : X \rightarrow Y$) denotes a function f of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) into a space (Y, σ) . Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure and the interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$, respectively.

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space X is said to be:

- (1) **regular open** [21] if $A = int(cl(A))$.
- (2) **semi-open** [13] if $A \subset cl(int(A))$.
- (3) **α -open** [19] if $A \subset int(cl(int(A)))$.

- (4) **β -open [1]** if $A \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(A)))$.
- (5) **γ -open [9]** if $A \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(A)) \cup \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$.
- (6) **ii-open [2]** set if there exists an open set $G \in \mathfrak{I}$, such that
- (i) $G \neq \emptyset, X$
 - (ii) $A \subset \text{cl}(A \cap G)$
 - (iii) $\text{int}(A) = G$.

The complement of a regular open (resp. semi-open, α -open, β -open, γ -open, ii-open,) set is called **regular closed** (resp. **semi-closed, α -closed, β -closed, γ -closed, ii-closed**).

The intersection of all α -closed (resp. β -closed, γ -closed, ii-closed, semi-closed) sets containing A is called the **α -closure** (resp. **β -closure, γ -closure, ii-closure, semi-closure**) of A and is denoted by **$\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$** (resp. **$\beta\text{-cl}(A)$, $\gamma\text{-cl}(A)$, **ii-cl(A), s-cl(A)**). Dually, the **α -interior** (resp. **β -interior, γ -interior, ii-interior, semi-interior**) of A , denoted by **$\alpha\text{-int}(A)$** (resp. **$\beta\text{-int}(A)$, $\gamma\text{-int}(A)$, **ii-int(A), s-int(A)**) is defined to be the union of all α -open (resp. β -open, γ -open, ii-open, semi-open) sets contained in A .****

The family of all ii-open (resp. ii-closed, regular open, regular closed, semi-open, semi-closed, α -open, α -closed, β -open, β -closed, γ -open, γ -closed) sets of a space X is denoted by **ii-O(X)** (resp. **ii-C(X), R-O(X), R-C(X), S-O(X), S-C(X), α -O(X), α -C(X), β -O(X), β -C(X), γ -O(X), γ -C(X)**).

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{I}) is said to be

- (1) **g-closed [14]**, if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (2) **s*g-closed [17]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \text{S-O}(X)$.
- (3) **β^* g-closed [20]** if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \beta\text{-O}(X)$.
- (4) **gs-closed [3]** if $\text{s-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (5) **sg-closed [6]** if $\text{s-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \text{S-O}(X)$.
- (6) **α g-closed [16]** if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (7) **α g-closed [16]** if $\alpha\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \alpha\text{-O}(X)$.
- (8) **γ g-closed [8]** if $\gamma\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (9) **γ g-closed [8]** if $\gamma\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \gamma\text{-O}(X)$.
- (10) **generalized ii-closed** (briefly **gii-closed**) if $\text{ii-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{I}$.
- (11) **ii-generalized closed** (briefly **iig-closed**) if $\text{ii-cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$.

The complement of ii-closed (resp. gii-closed, iig-closed, g-closed, α g-closed, α g-closed, γ g-closed, γ g-closed, gs-closed, sg-closed) set is said to be ii-open (resp. gii-open, iig-open, g-open, α g-open, α g-open, γ g-open, γ g-open, gs-open, sg-open,).

2.3 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (2) g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (3) β^* g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (4) s^* g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (5) s-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (6) gs-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (7) sg-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (8) α -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (9) αg -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (10) $g\alpha$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (11) ii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (12) gii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (13) iig-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (14) γ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (15) $g\gamma$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (16) γg -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.

2.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then

(1) closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(2) g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(3) β^* g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(4) s^* g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(5) s-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(6) gs-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(7) sg-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(8) α -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(9) α g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(10) $g\alpha$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(11) ii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(12) gii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(13) iig-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(14) γ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(15) $g\gamma$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(16) γ g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

2.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Then

(1) closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(2) g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(3) β^* g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(4) s^* -g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(5) s-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(6) gs-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(7) sg-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(8) α -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(9) α g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(10) $g\alpha$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(11) ii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(12) gii-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(13) iig-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(14) γ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(15) $g\gamma$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

(16) γ g-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, X, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}$.

3. ii-normal spaces

3.1 Definition. A space X is said to be **ii-normal** if for any pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.2 Definition. A space X is said to be **s-normal** [15] (resp. **α -normal** [5], **γ -normal** [8], **β^* -g-normal** [11]) if for any pair of disjoint closed sets A and B , there exist disjoint s-open (resp. α -open, γ -open, β^* -g-open) sets U and V such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3.3 Remark. The following diagram holds for a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) :

None of these implications is reversible as shown by the following examples.

3.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}\}$. Let $A = \{c\}$ and $B = \{d\}$ be closed sets, there exist disjoint s-open sets $U = \{a, c\}$ and $V = \{b, d\}$ such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is s-normal as well as ii-normal spaces also γ -normal spaces, since every s-open set is ii-open as well as γ -open. But it is not α -normal, since U and V are not α -open sets.

3.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \phi, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is γ -normal. But it is neither ii-normal nor s-normal.

3.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is normal as well as ii-normal.

3.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is normal as well as ii-normal.

3.8 Theorem. For a space X the following are equivalent:

- (1) X is ii-normal,
- (2) For every pair of open sets U and V whose union is X , there exist ii-closed sets A and B such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $A \cup B = X$,
- (3) For every closed set H and every open set K containing H , there exists an ii-open set U such that $H \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset K$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2) : Let U and V be a pair of open sets in an ii-normal space X such that $X = U \cup V$. Then $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint closed sets. Since X is ii-normal, there exist disjoint ii-open sets U_1 and V_1 such that $X - U \subset U_1$ and $X - V \subset V_1$. Let $A = X - U_1$, $B = X - V_1$. Then A and B are ii-closed sets such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $A \cup B = X$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) : Let H be a closed set and K be an open set containing H . Then $X - H$ and K are open sets whose union is X . Then by (2), there exist ii-closed sets M_1 and M_2 such that $M_1 \subset X - H$ and $M_2 \subset K$ and $M_1 \cup M_2 = X$. Then $H \subset X - M_1$, $X - K \subset X - M_2$ and $(X - M_1) \cap (X - M_2) = \phi$. Let $U = X - M_1$ and $V = X - M_2$. Then U and V are disjoint ii-open sets such that $H \subset U \subset X - V \subset K$. As $X - V$ is ii-closed set, we have $\text{ii-cl}(U) \subset X - V$ and $H \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset K$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1) : Let H_1 and H_2 be any two disjoint closed sets of X . Put $K = X - H_2$, then $H_2 \cap K = \phi$. $H_1 \subset K$, where K is an open set. Then by (3), there exists an ii-open set U of X such that $H_1 \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset K$. It follows that $H_2 \subset X - \text{ii-cl}(U) = V$, say, then V is ii-open and $U \cap V = \phi$. Hence H_1 and H_2 are separated by ii-open sets U and V . Therefore X is ii-normal.

4. Some related functions with ii-normal spaces

4.1 Definition . Let X be a topological space. A subset $N \subset X$ is called an **ii-neighbourhood** (briefly **ii-nhd**) [10] of a point $x \in X$ if there exist an ii-open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

4.2 Definition . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called

- (1) **R-map** [7] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is regular open in X for every regular open set V of Y ,
- (2) **completely continuous** [4] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is regular open in X for every open set V of Y ,
- (3) **rc-continuous** [12] if for each regular closed set F in Y , $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed in X .

4.3 Definition . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called

- (1) **pre ii-open** if $f(U) \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$ for each $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$,
- (2) **pre ii-closed** if $f(U) \in \text{ii-C}(Y)$ for each $U \in \text{ii-C}(X)$,
- (3) **almost ii-irresolute** if for each x in X and each ii-neighbourhood V of $f(x)$, $\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V))$ is an ii-neighbourhood of x .

4.4 Theorem . A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is pre ii-closed if and only if for each subset A in Y and for each ii-open set U in X containing $f^{-1}(A)$, there exists an ii-open set V containing A such that $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof: (\Rightarrow) : Suppose that f is pre ii-closed. Let A be a subset of Y and $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(A)$. Put $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is an ii-open set of Y such that $A \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

(\Leftarrow) : Let K be any ii-closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(K)) \subset X - K$ and $X - K \in \text{ii-O}(X)$. There exists an ii-open set V of Y such that $Y - f(K) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset X - K$. Therefore, we have $f(K) \supset Y - V$ and $K \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence, we obtain $f(K) = Y - V$ and $f(K)$ is ii-closed in Y . This shows that f is pre ii-closed.

4.5 Lemma. For a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the following are equivalent:

(1) f is almost ii-irresolute,

(2) $f^{-1}(V) \subset \text{ii-int}(\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V)))$ for every $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$.

4.6 Theorem. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost ii-irresolute if and only if $f(\text{ii-cl}(U)) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f(U))$ for every $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$.

Proof: (\Rightarrow) : Let $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$. Suppose $y \notin \text{ii-cl}(f(U))$. Then there exists $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$ such that $V \cap f(U) = \phi$. Hence, $f^{-1}(V) \cap U = \phi$. Since $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, we have $\text{ii-int}(\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V))) \cap \text{ii-cl}(U) = \phi$. Then by **Lemma 4.5**, $f^{-1}(V) \cap \text{ii-cl}(U) = \phi$ and hence $V \cap f(\text{ii-cl}(U)) = \phi$. This implies that $y \notin f(\text{ii-cl}(U))$.

(\Leftarrow) : If $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$, then $M = X - \text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V)) \in \text{ii-O}(X)$. By hypothesis, $f(\text{ii-cl}(M)) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f(M))$ and hence $X - \text{ii-int}(\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V))) = \text{ii-cl}(M) \subset f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(f(M))) \subset f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(f(X - f^{-1}(V)))) \subset f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(Y - V)) = f^{-1}(Y - V) = X - f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(V) \subset \text{ii-int}(\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(V)))$. By **Lemma 4.5**, f is almost ii-irresolute.

4.7 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a pre ii-open continuous almost ii-irresolute function from an ii-normal space X onto a space Y , then Y is ii-normal.

Proof: Let A be a closed subset of Y and B be an open set containing A . Then by continuity of f , $f^{-1}(A)$ is closed and $f^{-1}(B)$ is an open set of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset f^{-1}(B)$. As X is ii-normal, there exists an ii-open set U in X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset f^{-1}(B)$ by **Theorem 3.8**. Then, $f(f^{-1}(A)) \subset f(U) \subset f(\text{ii-cl}(U)) \subset f(f^{-1}(B))$. Since f is pre ii-open almost ii-irresolute surjection, we obtain $A \subset f(U) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f(U)) \subset B$. Then again by **Theorem 3.8**, the space Y is ii-normal.

4.8 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a pre ii-closed continuous function from an ii-normal space X onto a space Y , then Y is ii-normal.

Proof: Let M_1 and M_2 be disjoint closed sets. Then $f^{-1}(M_1)$ and $f^{-1}(M_2)$ are closed sets. Since X is ii-normal, then there exist disjoint ii-open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(M_1) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(M_2) \subset V$. By **Theorem 4.4**, there exist ii-open sets A and B such that $M_1 \subset A$, $M_2 \subset B$, $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$. Also, A and B are disjoint. Thus, Y is ii-normal.

4.9 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is called an α -space [12] if $\mathfrak{S} = \alpha\text{-O}(X)$.

4.9 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called α -closed [18] if for each closed set in X , $f(U)$ is α -closed set in Y .

4.8 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an α -closed continuous surjection and X is normal, then Y is ii-normal.

Proof: Let A and B be disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint closed sets of X by continuity of f . Since X is normal, there exist disjoint open sets U and V in X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$. By **Theorem 4.3 in [18]**, there exist disjoint α -open sets G and H in Y such that $A \subset G$ and $B \subset H$. Since every α -open set is ii-open, G and H are disjoint ii-open sets containing A and B , respectively. Therefore, Y is ii-normal.

5. Generalized ii-closed functions

5.1 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (1) **ii-closed** [10] if $f(A)$ is ii-closed in Y for each closed set A of X ,
- (2) **ii-g-closed** if $f(A)$ is ii-g-closed in Y for each closed set A of X ,
- (3) **gii-closed** if $f(A)$ is gii-closed in Y for each closed set A of X .

5.2 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (1) **quasi ii-closed** if $f(A)$ is closed in Y for each $A \in \text{ii-C}(X)$,
- (2) **ii-ii-g-closed** if $f(A)$ is ii-g-closed in Y for each $A \in \text{ii-C}(X)$,
- (3) **ii-gii-closed** if $f(A)$ is gii-closed in Y for each $A \in \text{ii-C}(X)$,
- (4) **almost gii-closed** if $f(A)$ is gii-closed in Y for each $A \in \text{R-C}(X)$.

5.3 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **ii-gii-continuous** if $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X for every $K \in \text{ii-C}(Y)$.

5.4 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **ii-irresolute** [10] if $f^{-1}(V) \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ for every $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$.

5.5 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be functions. Then

- (1) the composition $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is ii-gii-closed if f is ii-gii-closed and g is continuous ii-gii-closed.
- (2) the composition $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is ii-gii-closed if f is pre ii-closed and g is ii-gii-closed.
- (3) the composition $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ is ii-gii-closed if f is quasi ii-closed and g is gii-closed.

5.6 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be functions and let the composition $g \circ f : X \rightarrow Z$ be ii-gii-closed. If f is an ii-irresolute surjection, then g is ii-gii-closed.

Proof: Let $K \in \text{ii-C}(Y)$. Since f is ii-irresolute and surjective, $f^{-1}(K) \in \text{ii-C}(X)$ and $(g \circ f)(f^{-1}(K)) = g(K)$. Hence, $g(K)$ is gii-closed in Z and hence g is ii-gii-closed.

5.7 Lemma. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is ii-gii-closed if and only if for each subset B of Y and each $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(B)$, there exists a gii-open set V of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof: (\Rightarrow) : Suppose that f is ii-gii-closed. Let B be a subset of Y and $U \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(B)$. Put $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a gii-open set of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

(\Leftarrow) : Let K be any ii-closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(K)) \subset X - K$ and $X - K \in \text{ii-O}(X)$. There exists a gii-open set V of Y such that $Y - f(K) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset X - K$. Therefore, we have $f(K) \supset Y - V$ and $K \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence, we obtain $f(K) = Y - V$ and $f(K)$ is gii-closed in Y . This shows that f is ii-gii-closed.

5.8 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is continuous ii-gii-closed, then $f(H)$ is gii-closed in Y for each gii-closed set H of X .

Proof: Let H be any gii-closed set of X and V an open set of Y containing $f(H)$. Since $f^{-1}(V)$ is an open set of X containing H , $\text{ii-cl}(H) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f(\text{ii-cl}(H)) \subset V$. Since f is ii-gii-closed and $\text{ii-cl}(H) \in \text{ii-C}(X)$, we have $\text{ii-cl}(f(H)) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f(\text{ii-cl}(H))) \subset V$. Therefore, $f(H)$ is gii-closed in Y .

5.9 Remark. Every ii-irresolute function is ii-gii-continuous but not conversely.

5.10 Theorem. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is ii-gii-continuous if and only if $f^{-1}(V)$ is gii-open in X for every $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$.

5.11 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is closed ii-gii-continuous, then $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X for each gii-closed set K of Y .

Proof: Let K be a gii-closed set of Y and U an open set of X containing $f^{-1}(K)$. Put $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is open in Y , $K \subset V$, and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$. Therefore, we have $\text{ii-cl}(K) \subset V$ and hence $f^{-1}(K) \subset f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K)) \subset f^{-1}(V) \subset U$. Since f is ii-gii-continuous, $f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K))$ is gii-closed in X and hence $\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(K)) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K))) \subset U$. This shows that $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X .

5.12 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is closed ii-irresolute, then $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X for each gii-closed set K of Y .

5.13 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an open ii-gii-continuous bijection, then $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X for every gii-closed set K of Y .

Proof: Let K be a gii-closed set of Y and U an open set of X containing $f^{-1}(K)$. Since f is an open surjective, $K = f(f^{-1}(K)) \subset f(U)$ and $f(U)$ is open. Therefore, $\text{ii-cl}(K) \subset f(U)$. Since f is injective, $f^{-1}(K) \subset f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K)) \subset f^{-1}(f(U)) = U$. Since f is ii-gii-continuous, $f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K))$ is gii-closed in X and hence $\text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(K)) \subset \text{ii-cl}(f^{-1}(\text{ii-cl}(K))) \subset U$. This shows that $f^{-1}(K)$ is gii-closed in X .

5.14 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be functions and let the composition $\text{gof} : X \rightarrow Z$ be ii-gii-closed. If g is an open ii-gii-continuous bijection, then f is ii-gii-closed.

Proof: Let $H \in \text{ii-C}(X)$. Then $(\text{gof})(H)$ is gii-closed in Z and $g^{-1}((\text{gof})(H)) = f(H)$. By **Theorem 5.13**, $f(H)$ is gii-closed in Y and hence f is ii-gii-closed.

5.15 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $g : Y \rightarrow Z$ be functions and let the composition $\text{gof} : X \rightarrow Z$ be ii-gii-closed. If g is a closed ii-gii-continuous injection, then f is ii-gii-closed.

Proof: Let $H \in \text{ii-C}(X)$. Then $(\text{gof})(H)$ is gii-closed in Z and $g^{-1}((\text{gof})(H)) = f(H)$. By **Theorem 5.11**, $f(H)$ is gii-closed in Y and hence f is ii-gii-closed.

6. Preservation theorems and other characterizations of ii-normal spaces

6.1 Theorem. For a topological space X , the following are equivalent :

- (a) X is ii-normal,
- (b) for any pair of disjoint closed sets A and B of X , there exist disjoint gii-open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$,
- (c) for each closed set A and each open set B containing A , there exists a gii-open set U such that $\text{cl}(A) \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset B$,
- (d) for each closed A and each g-open set B containing A , there exists an ii-open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset \text{int}(B)$,
- (e) for each closed A and each g-open set B containing A , there exists a gii-open set G such that $A \subset G \subset \text{ii-cl}(G) \subset \text{int}(B)$,
- (f) for each g-closed set A and each open set B containing A , there exists an ii-open set U such that $\text{cl}(A) \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset B$,
- (g) for each g-closed set A and each open set B containing A , there exists a gii-open set G such that $\text{cl}(A) \subset G \subset \text{ii-cl}(G) \subset B$.

Proof: (a) \Leftrightarrow (b) \Leftrightarrow (c) : Since every ii-open set is gii-open, it is obvious.

(d) \Rightarrow (e) \Rightarrow (c) and (f) \Rightarrow (g) \Rightarrow (c) : Since every closed (resp. open) set is g-closed (resp. g-open), it is obvious.

(c) \Rightarrow (e) : Let A be a closed subset of X and B be a g-open set such that $A \subset B$. Since B is g-open and A is closed, $A \subset \text{int}(A)$. Then, there exists a gii-open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset \text{int}(B)$.

(e) \Rightarrow (d) : Let A be any closed subset of X and B be a g-open set containing A . Then there exists a gii-open set G such that $A \subset G \subset \text{ii-cl}(G) \subset \text{int}(B)$. Since G is gii-open, $A \subset \text{ii-int}(G)$. Put $U = \text{ii-int}(G)$, then U is ii-open and $A \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset \text{int}(B)$.

(c) \Rightarrow (g) : Let A be any g-closed subset of X and B be an open set such that $A \subset B$. Then $\text{cl}(A) \subset B$. Therefore, there exists a gii-open set U such that $\text{cl}(A) \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset B$.

(g) \Rightarrow (f) : Let A be any g-closed subset of X and B be an open set containing A . Then there exists a gii-open set G such that $\text{cl}(A) \subset G \subset \text{ii-cl}(G) \subset B$. Since G is gii-open and $\text{cl}(A) \subset G$, we have $\text{cl}(A) \subset \text{ii-int}(G)$, put $U = \text{ii-int}(G)$, then U is ii-open and $\text{cl}(A) \subset U \subset \text{ii-cl}(U) \subset B$.

6.2 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a continuous quasi ii-closed surjection and X is ii-normal, then Y is normal.

Proof: Let M_1 and M_2 be any disjoint closed sets of Y . Since f is continuous, $f^{-1}(M_1)$ and $f^{-1}(M_2)$ are disjoint closed sets of X . Since X is ii-normal, there exist disjoint $U_1, U_2 \in \text{ii-O}(X)$ such that $f^{-1}(M_i) \subset U_i$ for $i = 1, 2$. Put $V_i = Y - f(X - U_i)$, then V_i is open in Y , $M_i \subset V_i$ and $f^{-1}(V_i) \subset U_i$ for $i = 1, 2$. Since $U_1 \cap U_2 = \phi$ and f is surjective; we have $V_1 \cap V_2 = \phi$. This shows that Y is normal.

6.3 Lemma. A subset A of a space X is gii-open if and only if $F \subset \text{ii-int}(A)$ whenever F is closed and $F \subset A$.

6.4 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a closed ii-gii-continuous injection. If Y is ii-normal, then X is ii-normal.

Proof: Let N_1 and N_2 be disjoint closed sets of X , Since f is a closed injection, $f(N_1)$ and $f(N_2)$ are disjoint closed sets of Y . By the ii-normality of Y , there exist disjoint $V_1, V_2 \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$ such that $f(N_i) \subset V_i$ for $i = 1, 2$. Since f is ii-gii-continuous, $f^{-1}(V_1)$ and $f^{-1}(V_2)$ are disjoint gii-open sets of X and $N_i \subset f^{-1}(V_i)$ for $i = 1, 2$. Now, put $U_i = \text{ii-int}(f^{-1}(V_i))$ for $i = 1, 2$. Then, $U_i \in \text{ii-O}(X)$, $N_i \subset U_i$ and $U_1 \cap U_2 = \phi$. This shows that X is ii-normal.

6.5 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a closed ii-irresolute injection and Y is ii-normal, then X is ii-normal.

Proof: This is an immediate consequence since every ii-irresolute function is ii-gii-continuous.

6.6 Lemma. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost gii-closed if and only if for each subset B of Y and each $U \in \text{R-O}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(B)$, there exists a gii-open set V of Y such that $B \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

6.7 Lemma. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost gii-closed, then for each closed set M of Y and each $U \in \text{R-O}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(M)$, there exists $V \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$ such that $M \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

6.8 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a continuous almost gii-closed surjection. If X is normal, then Y is ii-normal.

Proof: Let M_1 and M_2 be any disjoint, closed sets of Y . Since f is continuous, $f^{-1}(M_1)$ and $f^{-1}(M_2)$ are disjoint closed sets of X . By the normality of X , there exist disjoint open sets U_1 and U_2 such that $f^{-1}(M_i) \subset U_i$, where $i = 1, 2$. Now, put $G_i = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U_i))$ for $i = 1, 2$, then $G_i \in \text{R-O}(X)$, $f^{-1}(M_i) \subset U_i \subset G_i$ and $G_1 \cap G_2 = \phi$. By **Lemma 6.7**, there exists $V_i \in \text{ii-O}(Y)$ such that $M_i \subset V_i$ and $f^{-1}(V_i) \subset G_i$, where $i = 1, 2$. Since $G_1 \cap G_2 = \phi$ and f is surjective, we have $V_1 \cap V_2 = \phi$. This shows that Y is ii-normal.

6.9 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a continuous ii-closed surjection and X is normal, then Y is ii-normal.

References

1. M. E. Abd EI-Monsef, S. N. EI Deeb and R. A. Mohamoud, β -open sets and β -continuous mappings, Bull. Fac. Assiut Univ. Sci., **12**(1983), 77-90.
2. A. Amir Mohammed and S. Beyda Abdullah, ii-open sets in topological spaces, International Mathematical Forum , Vol. 14, **1**(2019), 41-48.
3. S. P. Arya and T. Nour, Characterizations of s-normal spaces, Indian J. Pure Appl. Math., **21** (1990), 717-719.
4. S. P. Arya and R. Gupta, On strongly continuous functions, Kyungpook Math. J., **14** (1974), 131-141.
5. S. S. Benchalli and P. G. Patil, Some new continuous maps in topological spaces, Journal of Advanced Studies in Topology, **2/1-2**, (2009), 53-63.
6. P. Bhattacharyya and B. K. Lahiri, Semi generalized closed sets in topology, Indian J. Math., **29** (1987), 375-382.
7. D. Carnahan, Some properties related to compactness in topological spaces, PhD thesis, University of Arkansas, 1973.
8. E. Ekici, On γ -normal spaces, Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. Roumanie Tome, 50(98), **3**(2007), 259-272.
9. A. A. El-Atik, A study of some types of mappings on topological spaces, M. Sci. thesis, Tanta Univ., Egypt, 1997.
10. K. Hamant, ii-separation axioms in topological spaces, International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology (IJMTT), Vol. **65**, Issue 11, (2019).
11. K. Hamant, Brahampal Singh and Jitendra Kumar, β^* g-normal spaces in topological spaces, Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR), Vol. **6**, Issue 6, (2019), 897-907.
12. D. S. Jankovic', A note on mappings of extremally disconnected spaces, Acta Math. Hungar., **46** (1-2) (1985), 83-92.
13. N. Levine, Semiopen sets and semicontinuity in topological spaces, Amer. Math. Monthly, **70** (1963), 36-41.
14. N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo, **19** (2) (1970), 89-96.
15. S. N. Maheshwari and R. Prasad, On s-normal spaces, Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. R. S. Roumanie (N. S.), **22** (68) (1978), 27-29.
16. H. Maki, R. Devi and K. Balachandram, Associated topologies of generalized α -open and α -generalized closed sets, Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Math. **1**(1994), 51-63.
17. H. Maki, T. Noiri and M. Hussain, On s^* g-closed sets and s^* -normal spaces, JNSMAC, Vol. **48**, No. 1 & 2, (2008), 31-41.
18. T. Noiri, Almost continuity and some separation axioms, Glasnik Math., **9**(3), (1974), 131-135.
19. O. Njastad, On some classes of nearly open sets, Pacific J. Math., **15** (1965), 961-970.
20. M. C. Sharma and H. Kumar, On β^* g-closed sets and β^* -normal spaces, Acta Ciencia Indica, Vol. XLI, M No. 1, (2015), 3-12.
21. M. H. Stone, Applications of the theory of Boolean rings to general topology, Trans. Amer. Math. Soc., **41**(1937), 375-381.